

Transfer function-based generalization of grid forming power synchronization loops

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ABSTRACT

With the increasing penetration of inverter-based resources, grid forming control is expected to play a key role in stabilizing future grids. In these controllers, the power synchronization loop is in charge of synchronizing the inverter to the grid using an active power balance, removing the need for a phase-locked loop. Moreover, power synchronization loops can provide different services to the grid, including primary frequency regulation, inertial response or damping, among others. The aim of this work is to provide a generalization of power synchronization loops, classifying the existing strategies into six structures. Using their small-signal models, an analytical study is carried out, showing equivalences between controllers and identifying their main characteristics, limitations and tuning methodologies in grid-connected mode. The performance of different structures is also compared, evaluating their power setpoint tracking capability, the response against frequency excursions and the capability to filter phase jumps. Finally, analytical results are validated in an experimental testbench.

1. Introduction

The massive deployment of renewable energy resources into the power grid is a significant step toward achieving an environmentally friendly and sustainable energy system. However, unlike conventional generation plants, based on synchronous generators (SGs), renewable energy resources rely on power electronics for connecting to the grid. This paradigm shift brings new challenges from grid stability perspective [1].

The conventional approach to manage inverter-based resources (IBRs) has been the grid following control. In this mode, the inverter behaves as an equivalent current source that follows the grid. The synchronization with an existing grid is carried out through a phase-locked loop (PLL), measuring the voltage at the point of common coupling (PCC). However, the stability of these controllers is endangered as the penetration of IBRs increases [2]. On the one hand, the reduction of the grid inertia, traditionally provided by SGs rotating masses, leads to faster transients that cannot be tracked by PLLs [3]. On the other hand, the increase in the grid impedance, which reduces the voltage stiffness, has a negative impact on voltage-measurement based synchronization mechanisms [4].

In this context, grid forming control (GFM) has emerged as a promising solution to contribute to stabilizing IBR-dominated power grids [5]. In this mode, the inverter behaves as an equivalent voltage source. Frequency and voltage synchronization are achieved through active and reactive power balances, without the need of a PLL [6]. Different GFM strategies can be found in literature. The most common ones are the droop-based and the virtual synchronous generator-based (VSG) approaches [7]. In the former, the primary frequency and voltage regulation of conventional power plants is emulated. In the latter, the behavior of SGs is mimicked with different levels of detail [8]. Other advanced strategies include the matching control of the DC bus and non-linear controllers, such as virtual oscillators [9].

One of the key elements of the GFM controller is the power synchronization loop (PSL). It ensures the frequency synchronization between the IBR and the grid using an active power balance. Additionally, its structure will determine the services that can be provided to the grid [10]: primary frequency regulation, inertial response or damping power, among others. For achieving these services, different approaches have been proposed in literature.

Some PSLs will mimic the behavior of conventional generation systems, emulating damping winding of SGs or including power system

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stabilizers [11]. The lack of electromagnetic coupling in GFM inverters, requires a PLL to emulate damping windings, contradicting the GFM concept, in which the IBR should behave as an independently-controlled voltage source [12]. Moreover, its inner dynamics could interfere with the power dynamics [13,14], and its performance will be considerably limited in weak grid conditions [15]. The power system stabilizers, will not only increase the complexity, but they will also couple active and reactive power control, which is undesirable [10,16].

Taking advantage of the flexibility provided by GFM controllers, some authors have proposed adaptive PSLs [17,18]. These strategies could boost the performance both during normal operation and faults [19]. However, the non-linearities introduced by these PSLs hinders the analytical evaluation under massive integration of GFM inverters.

Taking into account the drawbacks of the previous strategies, linear PSLs that only rely on active power measurements are the most widespread structures. Despite having reduced number of inputs and fixed parameters, these structures can still provide high flexibility from service perspective. This flexibility can be achieved by increasing the degrees of freedom of the PSL, due to the lack of thermal nor mechanical constraints. Some modifications over classical PSL structures include derivative terms [20,21], high-pass filters [22,23], feed-forward terms [12,24], lead-lag structures [25–27] or parallelized structures [28,29].

The performance and services of linear PSLs are inherently determined by the location of the poles and zeros of the controller. Therefore, PSLs can be classified and analyzed based on their small-signal transfer function structures. The fundamental idea of using a generic transfer function in the PSL of GFM inverters was first introduced in [30] and was further formalized by [31], laying the foundations for this concept.

The aim of this work is to extend the generalization framework of the PSL structures already given in [31], which was limited to controllers with a first-order transfer function. The extension of the analysis to higher-order transfer functions was already highlighted in that reference as a research opportunity, which is addressed in detail in this work. By systematically covering all PSL strategies up to second-order system structures, this work provides a broader classification of PSL strategies into six possible structures, detailing their characteristics, grid services, limitations, and equivalences.

The work further contributes by proposing an analytical tuning methodology for the defined PSL structures. Explicit tuning equations are provided to address services such as primary frequency regulation, inertia, and system damping, taking into account grid characteristics. Moreover, this work introduces a frequency-domain analysis based on Network Frequency Perturbation (NFP) plots, which offer an intuitive interpretation of PSL dynamics compared to pole-zero location and time-domain simulations.

The proposed PSL structures are experimentally validated in a grid-connected setup, bridging the gap between theoretical transfer functions and practical implementation, confirming the validity of the proposed small-signal transfer function approach.

This work is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the simplified structure of an IBR operating in GFM mode, its small-signal model in grid-connected mode and the main transfer functions that are used to characterize the performance of the PSL. Once the small-signal model is presented, the six PSL structures are classified in Section 3, describing their main characteristics, the provided grid services and their tuning methodology. The equivalence between PSL structures and the control schemes proposed in literature is also addressed. In Section 4, the performance of the different PSLs is compared under some specific primary frequency regulation, inertia and damping requirements. The analysis is carried out analytically, using the transfer functions from previous sections. The analytical results are validated using an experimental setup in Section 5. Finally, conclusions are summed up in Section 6.

Fig. 1. Simplified one-line diagram of a GFM inverter.

2. Grid forming PSL modeling

The simplified single-line diagram of an IBR operating in GFM mode is shown in Fig. 1. The IBR can operate both in standalone (S_1 closed) or grid-connected mode (S_2 closed). In standalone mode, the IBR feeds passive loads, represented by Z_L . In grid-connected mode, the IBR exchanges power with a grid, represented using its Thévenin equivalent: a voltage source v_g and an impedance Z_g . An LC filter is used to meet the power quality requirements. For the sake of simplicity, an ideal DC voltage source is considered.

The GFM is composed of two control layers. The outer layer consists of the power synchronization loop (PSL) and the reactive power control (RPC). The PSL will generate the angular frequency ω_r , based on active power measurement P , and active power and angular frequency setpoints, P^* and ω_r^* . The RPC will generate the voltage amplitude E based on reactive power measurement Q , and reactive power and voltage amplitude setpoints, Q^* and E^* . The inner controller will generate the modulation voltage for the inverter. For the sake of simplicity, a GFM without inner controllers will be considered.

2.1. Small-signal model

The most common approach to model the active power loop is to use a quasi-stationary small-signal approach. The model is shown in Fig. 2, using per unit (pu) notation. It is usually valid for evaluating the performance of PSLs operating from DC up to 20 Hz, as it neglects the transient terms of the impedance [32]. The following assumptions are made:

- The GFM inverter is connected to a purely inductive grid, which is a valid approximation for most medium- and high-voltage networks.
- Outer loops are tuned in the range of a few Hz, without inner loops or with a bandwidth several times higher than outer loops.
- The grid is modeled as an infinite bus without internal dynamics. Grid frequency and phase angle variations are included as external inputs. These input perturbations represent typical grid events and allow for evaluating the response of the GFM controller without explicitly modeling the full grid dynamics.
- Both the GFM and the grid operate close to the rated voltage (1 pu), with a small phase shift δ between them.

Under these assumptions, active and reactive power can be decoupled, allowing the dynamics of the RPC to be neglected. The simplified active power expression is given by (1), where $X_{eq} = X_c + X_g$ is the total reactance seen by the inverter. Once linearized, active power becomes primarily dependent on the phase deviation $\Delta\delta$ and a synchronization constant, K_f , inversely proportional to X_{eq} . However, in grids with lower X/R ratio, such as those typical of low-voltage or microgrids environments, the decoupling of powers does no longer hold. The

Fig. 2. Small signal model of a grid connected GFM.

power transfer equations in such cases involve both voltage magnitude and angle variations, introducing coupling between active and reactive power dynamics. While the proposed classification of PSL structures remains valid in concept, the associated small-signal models and tuning procedures would require adaptation to accurately capture the effects of resistive components. Extending the analytical framework to include these cases is a valuable direction for future research.

$$P = \frac{E|v_g|}{X_{eq}} \sin \delta \rightarrow \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta \delta} \approx \frac{1}{X_{eq}} = K_t \quad (1)$$

When ω_r^* is not modified, the small-signal model of the PSL is composed of two inputs (power setpoint ΔP^* and feedback ΔP) and one output (angular frequency output $\Delta \omega_r$). The inner structure of the PSL includes two transfer functions: G_c , applied to the power error, and H_c , applied to the power feedback.

The grid model will use $\Delta \omega_r$ and grid frequency deviation $\Delta \omega_g$ to determine the exchanged active power according to (1). A phase deviation $\Delta \Phi$ input is also added to emulate phase jump perturbances, which are usually related to line modifications.

2.2. Small-signal transfer functions

In grid-connected mode, three characteristic transfer functions need to be evaluated: (1) the power setpoint tracking performance (2), (2) the response to grid frequency deviations (3) and (3) the capability to filter phase jumps (4).

$$\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta P^*} = \frac{G_c \omega_b K_t}{s + G_c H_c \omega_b K_t} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta \omega_g} = -\frac{\omega_b K_t}{s + G_c H_c \omega_b K_t} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\Delta \omega_r}{\Delta \Phi} = -\frac{G_c H_c K_t s}{s + G_c H_c \omega_b K_t} \quad (4)$$

The response to load power variations, characterized by (5), is also relevant in grid-connected operation. However, since active power and phase angle variations are directly related by Eq. (1), the frequency response to load perturbations is already captured by Eq. (4). Therefore, for the sake of conciseness, only the latter response is evaluated in this work.

$$\frac{\Delta \omega_r}{\Delta P} = -\frac{G_c H_c s}{s + G_c H_c \omega_b K_t} = \frac{1}{K_t} \frac{\Delta \omega_r}{\Delta \Phi} \quad (5)$$

In stand-alone mode, as the grid does not exist, the model is simplified according to Fig. 1. Only angular frequency response to load power perturbations needs to be evaluated (6):

$$\frac{\Delta \omega_r}{\Delta P} = -G_c H_c \quad (6)$$

From the previous transfer functions, the following key points can be concluded:

- Under rated frequency operation, $\Delta \omega_g = 0$, power setpoint tracking is only ensured if H_c has a unitary gain in steady-state. This

Fig. 3. Droop controller.

condition is required to achieve a null steady-state tracking error ($e_p^* = 0$) under a power setpoint step:

$$e_p^* = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} s \left(1 - \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta P^*} \right) \frac{1}{s} = 1 - \frac{1}{H_c} \Big|_{s=0} \quad (7)$$

- The frequency response coefficient, m_f , quantifies the GFM inverter power variation in response to a unit change in system frequency, providing information about the primary frequency regulation capability. It will depend on the inverse of $G_c H_c$ according to the final value theorem (8). A non-zero m_f value is required to contribute to frequency regulation and ensure stand-alone operation. Higher m_f values will increase primary frequency regulation contribution, but they can produce significant power variations even during minimal frequency deviations. This could potentially limit the ability to effectively share power with other grid-connected devices during a disturbance.

$$m_f = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} s \left(\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta \omega_g} \frac{1}{s} \right) = -\lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{G_c H_c} \Big|_{s=0} \quad (8)$$

- The rate of change of frequency under a power perturbation $RoCoF_p$ is defined as the initial angular frequency derivative of the GFM inverter under a power unitary step. It will only depend on $s G_c H_c$ according to the initial value theorem in (9). The same applies to the rate of change under a phase jump $RoCoF_\Phi$, as $\Delta \delta$ and ΔP are directly related by K_t (10). Usually, the inertia H (seconds) is used to characterize the $RoCoF_p$ limitation capability of a GFM inverter. Both are inversely related according to $RoCoF_p = 1/(2H)$.

$$RoCoF_p = \lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} s \left(\frac{s \Delta \omega_r}{\Delta P} \frac{1}{s} \right) = -\lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} s G_c H_c \quad (9)$$

$$RoCoF_\Phi = \lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} s \left(\frac{\Delta \omega_r}{\Delta \Phi} \frac{1}{s} \right) = K_t \cdot RoCoF_p \quad (10)$$

3. Classification of PSL structures

From the previous analysis, it is clear that transfer function $G_c H_c$ plays a key role in the performance of the GFM inverter. This transfer function will not only determine the power tracking dynamics, but also the response to grid disturbances. Hence, services such as primary frequency regulation, inertia and oscillation damping will be determined by $G_c H_c$. Attending to the poles and zeros of the previous transfer function, PSL schemes can be classified into six structures. These will be described in detail in the next subsections.

3.1. Gain

The simplest approach is to use a K gain in G_c and a unitary gain in H_c (11). This structure is known as droop control, where K is usually referred as droop gain m_p (Fig. 3).

$$G_c H_c = K \quad (11)$$

According to (8)–(10), this PSL will contribute to primary frequency regulation with an $m_f = 1/K$. However, it will not limit the $RoCoF$, making the system frequency susceptible to power perturbations. This PSL provides a fast primary frequency regulation capability, damping frequency oscillations without inertial response.

Fig. 4. Gain + pole PSLs.

Table 1
Gain + pole PSLs: equivalences.

	G_c	H_c	K	τ_p
Droop + error filter	$\frac{K}{\tau_p s + 1}$	1	m_p	τ_f
Droop + feedback filter	K	$\frac{1}{\tau_p s + 1}$	m_p	τ_f
VSG	$\frac{K}{\tau_p s + 1}$	1	$\frac{1}{D}$	$\frac{2H}{D}$

Its transfer functions in grid-connected mode are gathered in [Appendix A](#). The system will have a first-order characteristic equation, with a natural frequency depending on the PSL gain and grid strength, $\omega_n = K K_t \omega_b$. Hence, bandwidth and primary frequency regulation are coupled. Due to the limited bandwidth requirements of GFM inverters, typically below 5 Hz [33], small values of K are generally required for this strategy. This usually results in a high frequency response capability, as described in (8), diffculting the power-sharing capability.

3.2. Gain + pole

Primary frequency regulation and bandwidth can be decoupled by adding a pole ($1/\tau_p$), providing a low-pass filtered proportional response against power perturbations:

$$G_c H_c = \frac{K}{\tau_p s + 1} \quad (12)$$

This PSL structure is achieved adding a low-pass filter with a time constant τ_f to the droop control. The filter can be applied to the power error or feedback, leading to different power setpoint tracking dynamics. In VSGs, when the dynamics of the turbine and the governor are neglected, the inertia H and the damping D of the machine also lead to the same structure [34]. These PSLs are shown in [Fig. 4](#), and its equivalences are summed in [Table 1](#).

The addition of the pole will not modify the primary frequency regulation capability already discussed in [Section 3.1](#). However, it will limit the RoCoF under perturbations to K/τ_p , providing an equivalent inertia of $\tau_p/(2K)$ according (9). The system will also have a second order system behavior [Appendix A](#), with a natural frequency inversely related to the inertia of the system $\omega_n = \sqrt{K K_t \omega_b / \tau_p}$.

This PSL structure provides two degrees of freedom, K and τ_p , to manage three parameters of the system: the inertia/natural frequency, the damping and the primary frequency regulation. Hence, one of them will be dependent on the others. For instance, when the primary frequency regulation and the inertia are fixed, the damping coefficient ξ will be determined by (13). Providing a high inertial response with high damping usually requires a small K , which hinders the power sharing capability of the GFM.

$$\xi = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\tau_p}{K K_t \omega_b}} \quad (13)$$

Fig. 5. Gain + pole + zero PSLs.

Table 2
Gain + pole + zero PSLs: equivalences.

	G_c	H_c	K	τ_p	τ_z
Droop + lag compensator	K	$\frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_p s + 1}$	m_p	τ_f	$\alpha \tau_f$
VSG + derivative term	$\frac{K}{\tau_p s + 1}$	$\tau_z s + 1$	$\frac{1}{D}$	$\frac{2H}{D}$	k_d
VSG + parallel proportional	$\frac{K}{\tau_p s + 1}$	$\tau_z s + 1$	$\frac{k_d D + 1}{D}$	$\frac{2H}{D}$	$\frac{2H K_d}{K_d D + 1}$
VSG + phase feedforward	$K \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_p s + 1}$	1	$\frac{1}{D}$	$\frac{2H}{D}$	$\frac{k_d}{\omega_b}$

3.3. Gain + pole + zero

The addition of a zero ($1/\tau_z$) to the PSL transfer function has been proposed as an alternative to achieve higher flexibility, providing an extra degree of freedom to manage the damping of the system:

$$G_c H_c = K \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_p s + 1} \quad (14)$$

Literature has proposed several strategies to achieve this PSL structure, as summed in [Fig. 5](#). In droop controllers, the filter can be replaced by a lag-compensator [35,36]. The addition of a derivative action in the power feedback [20,21], a proportional parallel action [28,29] or an angle feedforward [12,24] are other approaches that have been proposed for both filtered droop and VSG strategies. Their parameter equivalences are summed in [Table 2](#). All of them can be tuned to provide the same response against perturbations, differing in the power setpoint tracking performance ([Appendix A](#)).

The additional zero will not modify the primary frequency regulation capability, and the system will still have a second order response characteristic equation. As in the previous structure, K and τ_p can be selected according to the primary frequency regulation and natural frequency of the characteristic equation. Then, the zero can set the damping:

$$\tau_z = \frac{2\xi \sqrt{\tau_p K K_t \omega_b} - 1}{K K_t \omega_b} \quad (15)$$

The main drawback of adding a zero is that the PSL loses the capability to limit the RoCoF under power perturbations (9). The initial $\Delta\omega$,

Fig. 6. PI controller.

Table 3

Gain + pole at origin + zero PSLs: equivalences.

	G_c	H_c	K	τ_z
VSG with $D = 0$ + derivative term	$\frac{K}{s}$	$\tau_z s + 1$	$\frac{1}{2H}$	k_d
VSG with $D = 0$ + Vert proportional	$\frac{K}{\tau_p s + 1}$	$\tau_z s + 1$	$\frac{1}{2H}$	$2Hk_d$
VSG with $D = 0$ + phase feedforward	$K \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{s}$	1	$\frac{1}{2H}$	$\frac{k_d}{\omega_d}$
PI controller	$K \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{s}$	1	k_i	$\frac{k_p}{k_i}$

variation under a power perturbation will increase with τ_z , according to:

$$\Delta\omega_r|_{t=0} = \lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} s \left(\frac{\Delta\omega_r}{\Delta P} \frac{1}{s} \right) = -K \frac{\tau_z}{\tau_p} \quad (16)$$

3.4. Gain + pole at origin + zero

A special case of the previous structure occurs when the real pole is replaced by a pole at the origin or an integrator (17). This structure is achieved when the strategies from Section 3.3 are applied to a VSG behaving as a pure inertia ($D = 0$). A PI controller, shown in Fig. 6, can also achieve this structure [37,38]. Parameter equivalences are summed in Table 3.

$$G_c H_c = K \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{s} \quad (17)$$

This structure will lose the primary frequency regulation and stand-alone operation capability, as its output under Eq. (8) becomes zero. This indicates that the steady-state power contribution will not change under frequency deviations. However, a steady-state power deviation will exist under a grid frequency ramp input as determined by (18). $1/K$ can be seen as the inertial contribution of the GFM at low frequency perturbations:

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} s \left(\frac{\Delta P}{s \Delta \omega_g} \frac{1}{s} \right) = -1/K \quad (18)$$

The gain K of this PSL is usually tuned to ensure an inertial response at low frequencies. It will also determine the natural frequency of its characteristic equation $\omega_n = \sqrt{K K_i \omega_b}$. Then, τ_z is selected to ensure a minimum damping:

$$\tau_z = \frac{2\xi}{\sqrt{K K_i \omega_b}} \quad (19)$$

This strategy will also lose the capability limit the RoCoF under power perturbations. In this case, the initial $\Delta\omega_r$ under a power perturbation will depend on $K\tau_z$.

3.5. Gain + 2 poles + zero

Since the addition of a zero not only decouples primary frequency regulation and damping, but also makes the system sensitive to power

Fig. 7. Gain + 2 pole + zero PSLs.

perturbations, an additional pole ($1/\tau_p'$) can be added to face this issue:

$$G_c H_c = K \frac{1}{\tau_p s + 1} \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_p' s + 1} \quad (20)$$

The most common strategy to achieve this PSL structure is to add a lead compensator with a gain α and a time constant τ_d to VSGs or filtered droops (Fig. 7(a)) [26,27]. This is equivalent to low-pass filtering the k_d term in Section 3.3. Another approach is to use a high-pass filtered (HPF) damping term D_d in the VSG, which will only act during transients, as in Fig. 7(b) [22,23]. Parameter equivalences are summed in Table 4. The coupling between parameters is higher in the former, making its tuning more complex.

The addition of τ_p' can limit the RoCoF and make the system less susceptible to power perturbations. According to (9), this will depend on:

$$RoCoF_p = - \lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} s G_c H_c = -K \frac{\tau_z}{\tau_p \tau_p'} \quad (21)$$

The characteristic equation of the system will increase to a 3rd order system, which is usually tuned using numerical methods [26]. The most common approach is to tune K and τ_p according to previous strategies. Then, a trade-off between RoCoF limitation and stability is required for tuning τ_p' and τ_z , as improving one will deteriorate the other. For a certain RoCoF, (21) provides a fixed relation between these time constants. A parameter sweep can be used to ensure a minimum phase margin with an acceptable RoCoF.

3.6. Gain + pole at origin + pole + zero

As in Section 3.4, the previous strategy can also replace one of its real poles for a pole at origin, removing the primary frequency regulation capability and providing an inertial response at low frequencies. The table of equivalences is summed in Table 5.

$$G_c H_c = K \frac{1}{s} \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_p' s + 1} \quad (22)$$

This PSL structure provides a pure inertial response with RoCoF limitation capability. Once the inertia is tuned (K), different strategies can be followed to tune τ_z and τ_p' , such as minimizing RoCoF [25] or ensuring a minimum phase margin [39]. As already mentioned in Section 3.5, a trade-off between RoCoF limitation and phase margin is always required.

3.7. Summary

A summary of the PSL structures attending to their response to power perturbations $G_c H_c$ is given in Table 6. The capability of the PSL to provide different services such as primary frequency regulation, inertia, RoCoF limitation, and its capability to decouple damping from primary frequency regulation, will depend on the degrees of freedom of the PSL, closely related to the number of poles and zeros.

Table 4
Gain + 2 pole + zero PSLs: equivalences.

	G_c	H_c	K	τ_p	$\tau_{p'}$	τ_z
VSG + lead-lag	$K \frac{1}{\tau_p s + 1}$	$\frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_{p'} s + 1}$	$\frac{1}{D}$	$\frac{2H}{D}$	τ_d	$\alpha \tau_d$
VSG + HPF droop	$K \frac{1}{\tau_p s + 1} \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_{p'} s + 1}$	1	$\frac{1}{D}$	$\frac{4H \tau_d}{-2H - \tau_d D - D_d \tau_d \pm \sqrt{(2H + \tau_d D + D_d \tau_d)^2 - 8H \tau_d D}}$		τ_d

Table 5
Gain + pole at origin + pole + zero PSLs: equivalences.

	G_c	H_c	K	$\tau_{p'}$	τ_z
VSG with D = 0 + lead-lag	$\frac{K}{s}$	$\frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_{p'} s + 1}$	$\frac{1}{2H}$	τ_d	$\alpha \tau_d$
VSG with D = 0 + HPF droop	$\frac{K}{s} \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_{p'} s + 1}$	1	$\frac{1}{2H + \tau_d D_d}$	$\frac{2H \tau_d}{2H + \tau_d D_d}$	τ_d

Table 6
Performance of different PSL structures attending to power perturbances.

Structure	$G_c H_c$	Frequency regulation	Inertia	Decoupled damping and freq. regulation	RoCoF limitation
Gain	K	✓	x	x	x
Gain Pole	$\frac{K}{\tau_p s + 1}$	✓	✓	x	✓
Gain Pole Zero	$K \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_p s + 1}$	✓	✓	✓	x
Gain 2 Pole Zero	$\frac{K}{\tau_p s + 1} \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_{p'} s + 1}$	✓	✓	✓	✓
Gain Pole at origin	$K \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{s}$	x	✓	✓	x
Gain Pole at origin Zero	$\frac{K}{s} \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_{p'} s + 1}$	x	✓	✓	✓

A structure with a zero and two real poles provides the highest flexibility from service perspective. However, a trade-off between RoCoF limitation and stability is always needed. Additional poles and zeros could be added, increasing the complexity of the PSL with minor improvements over the already described PSL structures.

For the same $G_c H_c$ transfer function, different power setpoint tracking dynamics can be achieved depending on the structure of G_c and H_c , as shown in Appendix A. The bandwidth of the power setpoint tracking can be increased by adding a zero, which will also lead to a more oscillatory response. As the zero only depends on the PSL parameters, any of the strategies can be achieved by adding a F_c block which only modifies the power setpoint dynamics. The scheme is shown in Fig. 8.

4. Analytical comparative

To compare the performance of PSLs, the Bode plots from Eqs. (2)–(4) are evaluated for a grid with $K_f = 1/0.3$ pu. The parameters of the PSL are summed in Table 7. The structure of G_c and H_c is selected in order to remove the zeros from $\Delta P/\Delta P^*$. The gain-based PSL is neglected from the analysis.

The first three strategies in the table are those with primary frequency regulation capability: gain + pole, gain + pole + zero, and gain + 2 pole + zero. The gain is set to $K = 0.05$ pu, providing full

Fig. 8. Modifying the dynamics of the power setpoint tracking capability.

Table 7
Structure and parameters of the PSLs.

Structure	G_c	H_c	K	τ_p	τ_z	$\tau_{p'}$
Gain Pole	$\frac{K}{\tau_p s + 1}$	1	0.05	0.4		
Gain Pole Zero	$\frac{K}{\tau_p s + 1}$	$\tau_z s + 1$	0.05	0.4	0.0543	
Gain 2 Pole Zero	$\frac{K}{(\tau_p s + 1)(\tau_{p'} s + 1)}$	$\tau_z s + 1$	0.05	0.4	0.065	0.0081
Gain Pole at origin Zero	$\frac{K}{s}$	$\tau_z s + 1$	0.125		0.0734	
Gain Pole at origin Pole Zero	$\frac{K}{s(\tau_{p'} s + 1)}$	$\tau_z s + 1$	0.125		0.095	0.0119

rated power variation under a grid frequency deviation of 5%. The time constant τ_p is set to 0.4 s. For the first PSL structure, this will ensure an inertial response of 4 s and a natural frequency of 1.82 Hz. However, a poorly damped system is achieved ($\xi = 0.11$). In the second strategy, a zero is used to improve the stability. A minimum phase margin of 45° is set as criterion, which is equivalent to a $\xi = 0.42$. For the third strategy, a phase margin of 45° and an initial RoCoF_p = 1 pu/s are considered as tuning conditions.

The fourth and fifth strategies are those which do not provide primary frequency regulation. The gain is tuned to ensure a inertial response of 4 s under low frequencies. This will yield the same natural frequency of 1.82 Hz. The criteria for tuning the zero and the additional pole are the same as in the previous cases.

4.1. Power setpoint tracking performance

The $\Delta P/\Delta P^*$ Bode response is shown in Fig. 9(a). The PSL with a gain and a pole provides the highest bandwidth, at the cost of having

Fig. 9. Bodes of the different PSL strategies.

the highest resonance peak. This will lead to an oscillatory response, with a high settling time.

The zero of the remaining strategies will improve the damping of the system, which is translated into a reduced settling time, but it will slightly reduce the bandwidth of the controller. The addition of a second pole will have a minimum impact on the bandwidth of the controller, as it is not dominant due to its high frequency. Compared to the strategies which only add a zero, a slight reduction of the resonance peak can be identified. The higher attenuation at high frequencies will also impact the rising time of the system.

The bandwidth of the system will be mainly dependent on the inertial response of the system, which sets the natural frequency of the characteristic equation. In all the cases, the bandwidth will be below 2 Hz. This is an issue when trying to achieve fast tracking response and slow response to power perturbations [40]. In this context, strategies that include additional terms over the power setpoint dynamics (Fig. 8) have been proposed in [38,41]. These strategies will rely on proper grid parameter identification and may become difficult to tune in complex grids. Hence, these strategies are out of the scope of this work.

4.2. Response to grid frequency deviations

The $\Delta P/\Delta\omega_g$ Bode response, also known as the network frequency perturbation plot [32], is shown in Fig. 9(b). It provides a graphical insight of the performance of the different PSLs from primary frequency regulation, inertial response and damping capability perspective.

The strategies with primary frequency regulation will be characterized by a low frequency region in which the exchanged active power opposes grid frequency changes (180° phase shift). The lower K , the higher the amplitude of this region will be. Then, magnitude and phase will start to increase up to the resonance peak, showing the combined action of the primary frequency regulation and an inertial response. Typical inertial region usually goes between 0.2 and 2 Hz, at which the inertia is dominant over the droop region.

The strategies without primary frequency regulation, on the other hand, will show a pure inertial response at low frequencies, characterized by a 20 dB/dec gain and a phase of 270°. This is translated into a power which opposes the derivative of the grid frequency.

Inertial systems will have a resonance that occurs at the natural frequency of the system. The natural frequency of the system, usually in

the range of 1–3 Hz, will mainly depend on PSL parameters and grid K_r . After the resonance, the GFM response is characterized by a decrease of the amplitude response with the frequency of the perturbation. The phase is also reduced, leveling at 90°. This region is related to the positive synchronization power component, which is characterized by an active power variation in phase with $\Delta\delta$ (90° phase advance with respect to grid frequency). This region is characteristic of grid forming controllers. In grid following strategies, the phase does not level off and it will continue to decrease, endangering the stability of the system.

4.3. Phase jump filtering capability

Phase jumps are characterized by a sudden change in δ , usually due to a line tripping or reclosing event. An IBR operating in GFM should smooth phase jumps by outputting a small $\Delta\omega_r$ during the event. The $\Delta\omega_r/\Delta\Phi$ transfer function for the previous cases are represented in Fig. 9(c).

Below the resonance frequency, all the strategies show a similar performance against phase jumps, as this region is mainly determined by the strength of the grid (K_r). However, the impact of the PSL can be clearly identified in frequencies above resonance.

As already discussed, the gain + pole PSL will provide the highest attenuation to high frequency terms, contributing to provide a low RoCoF under phase jumps or any power perturbations. However, the high resonance due to the limited damping will lead to long transients.

Those strategies which include a zero will not attenuate the high frequency gains. This is because the zero cancels the effect of the pole at high frequencies. It can also be seen as a power perturbation which is directly applied to the angular frequency without passing through the integral action (Fig. 5(c)). For the same phase margin, the strategy with primary frequency regulation will show better phase jump filtering capability, as the required τ_z is smaller. This is because the primary frequency regulation term contributes to the damping of the system.

Adding a second pole will provide an intermediate performance between the gain + pole strategy and the gain + pole + zero strategy. In this case, a trade-off between stability and phase jump filtering capability is required.

Fig. 10. Test bench for experimental validation.

5. Experimental validation

The previous PSL structures are validated in the experimental setup shown in Fig. 10. The setup consists of two converters connected in back-to-back topology. One of them is operated as a single-phase controlled rectifier to generate a stiff 320 V dc bus. The second one is used as a 3-phase inverter to test GFM strategies. All of the power electronic devices are based on INF-50 power inverters from Dutt Electronics. The grid is emulated using a 320-AMX bidirectional 3-phase power supply from Pacific Power. The inverter and the grid are coupled using a LC filter, and inductors that emulate the grid impedance. Damping resistors are included in series with the capacitor to attenuate filter resonance. All the passive elements and sensing devices are off-the-shelf components. The control algorithms, the acquisition task and the grid management are centralized in an OP4512 from OPAL-RT. The main parameters of the experimental setup are summed in Table 8.

PSLs are tested against power setpoint modifications, grid frequency perturbations and phase jumps. For these tests, the angular frequency and the power exchanged by GFM are captured at a sampling rate of 10 kHz. The active power measurement includes three post-filtering stages. A 50 Hz notch filter to remove the noise related to synchronous resonance [42]. This phenomena depends on the inductor transient terms (neglected in quasi-stationary model), and PSL structure has minor impact on it. A 100 Hz notch filter to remove the negative sequence ripple. Finally, a 300 Hz first order low-pass filter is included to remove high frequency noise. As the analysis is based on slow dynamics, these filters will have a minimum impact on the obtained results.

5.1. Power setpoint step

Fig. 11 shows the power response of the PSLs under a power setpoint step of 0.1 pu at $t=0.5$ s. The angular frequency setpoint of the GFM inverter matches the grid frequency $\omega_r^* = \omega_g$, and hence, all PSL strategies can track the power setpoint without steady-state error.

Table 8
Experimental setup parameters.

Base values					
S_b	625 W	v_b	200 V	ω_b	314 rad/s
Converter general values					
f_{sw}	10 kHz	v_{dc}	300 V		
LC filter					
L_c	0.1 pu	R_c	0.06 pu	C_f	0.05 pu
R_f	0.08 pu				
Operating point					
P^*	0 pu	ω_r^*	1 pu	Q^*	0 pu
E	1 pu				
Grid					
v_g	1 pu	ω_g	1 pu	L_g	0.2 pu

Fig. 11. Experimental power response under a power setpoint step of 0.1 pu.

Different transient responses are expected for PSLs according to analytical bodes from Fig. 9(a). The gain + pole PSL configuration exhibits a poorly damped response, resulting in a significant overshoot and longer settling time. For this second order system, the theoretical overshoot M_p and settling time t_s can be analytically derived from its damping coefficient and natural frequency characteristics using (23) and (24). The gain + pole PSL ($\xi = 0.11$ and $\omega_n = 1.98 \cdot 2\pi$ rad/s) has a theoretical overshoot of 0.71 and a settling time of 3.2 s. Experimentally measured overshoot results in 0.72, with a settling time slightly exceeding the 3 s. However, precise settling time measurement is challenging due to the ripple present in the power signal.

$$M_p = e^{\frac{-\pi\xi}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}}} \quad (23)$$

$$t_s = \frac{4}{\xi\omega_n} \quad (24)$$

Adding a zero to the PSL maintains the second order system response of the power setpoint. The natural frequency is kept unmodified, whereas the damping coefficient is increased to $\xi = 0.42$. Using (23)–(24), the overshoot and settling time are predicted to decrease to 0.23 and 0.83 s respectively. Experimentally measured overshoot is 0.25, and the settling time is above 0.8 s, matching expected values. The same power response is observed both with primary frequency regulation (gain + pole + zero PSL) and without it (gain + pole at origin + zero). This is because both strategies have been tuned to have the same natural frequency and damping characteristics.

Introducing a second pole in the PSL will transform the power setpoint dynamics into a third-order system. The additional pole slightly reduces the resonance compared to the second-order system (see Fig. 9(a)), impacting the overshoot. For the PSL without primary frequency regulation (gain + pole at origin + pole + zero PSL), the overshoot reduction is negligible. However, when two real poles are

(a) Grid frequency profile

(b) Power response of the PSL structures

Fig. 12. Experimental power response under a grid frequency perturbation.

used in the PSL, the overshoot is nearly halved (0.12). The third-order system structure should also attenuate high-frequency components compared to the second-order systems, impacting the settling time. However, its impact is minimal and difficult to observe experimentally due to the power signal ripple.

5.2. Grid frequency perturbation

To evaluate the performance under a grid frequency perturbations, the grid frequency amplitude is varied by $\Delta\omega_g = -0.01$ pu. Starting at 1 pu (50 Hz), the frequency decreases linearly to 0.99 pu (49.5 Hz) at a rate of 0.01 pu/s (0.5 Hz/s). The grid frequency transient begins at $t = 0.5$ s and concludes at $t = 1.5$ s, as illustrated in Fig. 12(a). The power responses for the different PSL structures are given in Fig. 12(b). As the grid frequency decreases, all PSL structures increase active power injection into the grid, contributing to system stability by supporting the active power balance.

As already observed in Section 5.1, the pole + gain PSL structure exhibits the least damped response due to the resonance peak in its transfer function (see Fig. 9(b)). In contrast, in the remaining strategies, this resonance is attenuated by the addition of a zero, effectively removing the low-frequency oscillations.

This test confirms the primary frequency regulation and inertial power contribution of the PSL strategies. For PSLs with primary frequency regulation, the steady-state active power response depends on the inverse of the controller static gain and the amplitude of $\Delta\omega_g$, as already described in (8). With a static gain tuned to 0.05, all such strategies should exhibit an identical frequency regulation contribution of 0.2 pu, which matches the experimental results.

Strategies incorporating a pole at the origin do not provide primary frequency regulation, as their active power returns to the setpoint after the perturbation. However, they will contribute to frequency stability during the transient, providing inertial power. Under a frequency ramp, these strategies will contribute with an inertial power determined by the rate of change of frequency of the grid and the PSL static gain, as described in (18). For a RoCoF of 0.01 pu/s and a $K = 0.125$, a steady-state active power of 0.08 pu is expected under a frequency ramp, which matches the experimental measurement. In those PSL structures with primary frequency regulation, the power response during the frequency ramp will be the sum of the primary frequency regulation power and the inertial power.

The addition of a second pole has negligible impact on the power response during frequency perturbations, as its effect is limited to high-frequency dynamics. While a slight delay is introduced in the time response, it does not significantly affect overall system performance.

5.3. Phase jump

Fig. 13(a) shows the angular frequency output of the PSLs under a phase jump of 2° at $t = 0.5$ s. A closer view of the angular frequency response during this event is given in Fig. 13(b). As expected from the analytical study, the PSL with a gain + pole configuration exhibits the best performance in terms of RoCoF limitation capability. Introducing a zero in the PSL minimizes its capability, while the addition of a second pole results in an intermediate response between the previous cases. This latter case requires a trade-off between stability and RoCoF limitation.

The PSL structure also affects to the high-frequency noise filtering capability of ω_r . In real systems, there is an active power ripple which is caused by grid unbalances, harmonic and/or measurement noise. In this context, PSL strategies with the same number of poles and zeros, such as “Gain + pole + zero” and “Gain + pole at origin + zero”, tend to be more sensitive to active power ripple due to their limited high-frequency filtering capability. In contrast, structures with a higher number of poles than zeros exhibit better noise rejection characteristics, thanks to the decaying magnitude of $\Delta\omega_r/\Delta P$ in the high-frequency range”.

It should be noted that the analytical comparison of PSL structures relies on a quasi-stationary model, which does not fully represent the real system dynamics. This model neglects inductor transient terms ($L \cdot di/dt$), which prevent instantaneous changes in the current. These transient terms act as an additional low-pass filtering stage for grid events, altering the real system response in the high frequency range (> 20 Hz). As a result, the $\Delta\omega_r/\Delta\Phi$ transfer function is affected, especially for PSL structures with a limited high frequency attenuation. For example, strategies with a constant gain at high frequencies (gain + pole + zero configuration) will exhibit some RoCoF limitation capability due to inductor’s transient terms. Consequently, the real system will not have a frequency jump, but rather a steep but finite RoCoF, as shown in Fig. 13(b).

The maximum RoCoF will not be produced right after the phase jump, as expected in the analytical study. Instead, the RoCoF will have a small transient until its maximum value is reached. For calculating the experimental RoCoF limitation capability of the PSLs, the derivative of the angular frequency response is computed, as shown in Fig. 14, and its maximum value is measured. The high ripple existing in the gain + pole + zero strategies do not allow a proper RoCoF estimation. While applying a filtering stage could mitigate this ripple, it would also alter the true RoCoF limitation capability of the system, and hence, these are ignored.

A comparison of the analytical and experimental results are summarized in Table 9. For PSL structures with RoCoF limitation capability, analytical and experimental results align when the high frequency components of $\Delta\omega_r/\Delta\Phi$ are properly filtered by the PSL. This occurs in the gain + pole structure, where both analytical and experimental

(a) Full capture

(b) Zoom at t = 0.5 s

Fig. 13. Experimental angular frequency under a phase jump of 2°.

Fig. 14. RoCoF calculation based on ω_r derivative.

maximum RoCoF is 0.015 pu/s. When an additional pole and zero are introduced, the high-frequency filtering capability is reduced, and the impact of the inductor transient term becomes more pronounced. This leads to deviations of up to 20%, with the quasi-stationary model underestimating the RoCoF limitation capability of the real system. In the case of gain + pole + zero structures, if the initial RoCoF is ignored, the maximum frequency deviation is higher than the analytical one. This phenomenon arises from synchronous resonance-induced overshoot, a characteristic behavior of voltage sources operating in RL systems [42]. Hence, the performance of these PSL structures will be further deteriorated.

Table 9

Theoretical vs experimental RoCoF_φ and Δω_{r|t=0} values.

Structure	Theoretical		Experimental	
	RoCoF _φ	Δω _{r t=0}	RoCoF _φ	Δω _{r t=0}
Gain + pole	0.015	0	0.015	0
Gain + pole + zero	∞	0.0008	-	0.001
Gain + 2 pole + zero	0.116	0	0.095	0
Gain + pole at origin + zero	∞	0.001	-	0.0013
Gain + pole at origin + pole + zero	0.116	0	0.105	0

From the previous comparison of analytical and experimental results, it is found that those strategies with faster dynamics (higher gain in the high frequency range of Fig. 9(c)) will require a more detailed modeling for estimating real RoCoF. In general, the quasi-stationary model will underestimate the RoCoF capability. Nevertheless, it still remains a simple and sufficiently accurate method for evaluating the performance of different controllers.

Finally, it should also be noted that primary frequency regulation influences the phase jump filtering capability of PSLs. When a PSL with and without primary frequency regulation are tuned to have the same natural frequency and phase margin, the one with frequency regulation requires smaller τ_z terms, as demonstrated in Appendix B. Since the RoCoF limitation is proportional to τ_z , a higher primary frequency regulation coefficient improves the PSL capability to limit RoCoF. Additionally, it will also lead to lower frequency nadirs.

6. Conclusions

This work has proposed a generalization of GFM power synchronization loops. By evaluating the small-signal power perturbation response, this work has shown that existing PSLs can be classified into six structures. The main characteristics of the transfer functions are addressed, describing its frequency services, its limitations and tuning methodologies. It is shown that the flexibility of the PSLs is increased as their number of poles and zeros are increased. However, as some of these services oppose to each other (e.g., damping and RoCoF limitation), a trade-off is always required. A controller with two real poles and a zero can be used to provide all frequency services: primary frequency regulation, inertia, damping and RoCoF. Increasing the number of poles and zeros will have minimum impact on the performance.

An analytical comparison of the different PSL structures under specific operating conditions is carried out. This analysis is focused on transfer function Bode analysis, which provides a graphical insight of their performance. First, the power setpoint tracking capability is evaluated. For the same PSL structure, different power tracking capabilities can be achieved depending on G_c and H_c values. However, the characteristic equation of the system will always be the same, requiring a trade-off between bandwidth and resonance/oscillatory response. Then, the response of the GFM to perturbations is evaluated. The active power response to frequency perturbation Bode can graphically identify the primary frequency regulation, inertial response and damping capability of the system. The response to phase jumps can be used to understand the frequency filtering capability of GFM inverters.

Analytical results have been validated experimentally. While the experimental power setpoint tracking and the response to frequency perturbations match analytical results, a deviation is found in the performance against phase jumps. The main reason for this deviation is the grid modeling approach, based on a quasi-stationary system. A model that considers the dynamic terms of the impedance would provide closer results, but it would also increase the complexity of the previous analysis. Despite this deviation, the quasi-stationary approach is still a valid and simple method to understand and evaluate the merits and demerits of each PSL structure in the low frequency range.

It should be noted that the conclusions of this work are based on modeling the grid as an infinite bus without internal dynamics,

Table A.10
Grid-connected mode transfer function for different PSL structures.

Structure	G_c	H_c	Characteristic equation $\beta = \text{num}(s + G_c H_c \omega_b K_T)$	$\Delta P / \Delta P^*$	$\Delta P / \Delta \omega_g$	$\Delta \omega_r / \Delta \Phi$
Gain	K	1	$s + K K_T \omega_b$	$\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T \omega_b$	$-\frac{1}{\beta} K_T \omega_b$	$-\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T s$
Gain Pole	$\frac{K}{\tau_p s + 1}$	1	$\tau_p s^2 + s + K K_T \omega_b$	$\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T \omega_b$	$-\frac{1}{\beta} K_T \omega_b (\tau_p s + 1)$	$-\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T s$
	K	$\frac{1}{\tau_p s + 1}$		$\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T \omega_b (\tau_p s + 1)$		
Gain Pole Zero	$\frac{K}{\tau_p s + 1}$	$\tau_z s + 1$	$\tau_p s^2 + (1 + \tau_z K K_T \omega_b) s + K K_T \omega_b$	$\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T \omega_b$	$-\frac{1}{\beta} K_T \omega_b (\tau_p s + 1)$	$-\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T s (\tau_z s + 1)$
	$K \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_p s + 1}$	1		$\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T \omega_b (\tau_z s + 1)$		
	K	$\frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_p s + 1}$		$\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T \omega_b (\tau_p s + 1)$		
Gain Pole at origin Zero	$\frac{K}{s}$	$\tau_z s + 1$	$s^2 + \tau_z K K_T \omega_b s + K K_T \omega_b$	$\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T \omega_b$	$-\frac{1}{\beta} K_T \omega_b s$	$-\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T s (\tau_z s + 1)$
	$K \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_p s + 1}$	1		$\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T \omega_b (\tau_z s + 1)$		
Gain 2 Poles Zero	$\frac{K}{(\tau_p s + 1)(\tau_{p'} s + 1)}$	$\tau_z s + 1$	$\tau_p \tau_{p'} s^3 + (\tau_p + \tau_{p'}) s^2 + \tau_z K K_T \omega_b s + K K_T \omega_b$	$\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T \omega_b$	$-\frac{1}{\beta} K_T \omega_b (\tau_p s + 1)$	$-\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T s (\tau_z s + 1)$
	$K \frac{\tau_z s + 1}{(\tau_p s + 1)(\tau_{p'} s + 1)}$	1		$\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T \omega_b (\tau_z s + 1)$	$1)(\tau_{p'} s + 1)$	
	$\frac{K}{\tau_p s + 1}$	$\frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_{p'} s + 1}$		$\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T \omega_b (\tau_{p'} s + 1)$		
Gain Pole at origin Pole Zero	$\frac{K}{s(\tau_{p'} s + 1)}$	$\tau_z s + 1$	$\tau_{p'} s^3 + s^2 + \tau_z K K_T \omega_b s + K K_T \omega_b$	$\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T \omega_b$	$-\frac{1}{\beta} K_T \omega_b s (\tau_{p'} s + 1)$	$-\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T s (\tau_z s + 1)$
	$\frac{K}{s(\tau_p s + 1)(\tau_{p'} s + 1)}$	1		$\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T \omega_b (\tau_z s + 1)$		
	$\frac{K}{s}$	$\frac{\tau_z s + 1}{\tau_{p'} s + 1}$		$\frac{1}{\beta} K K_T \omega_b (\tau_{p'} s + 1)$		

which allows for a simple classification and evaluation of PSL structures based only on inverter-side behavior. While this approach simplifies the analysis and supports direct comparison between control strategies, it does not capture the dynamic interactions that would arise if the grid were modeled as an aggregated synchronous generator with finite inertia and damping. Such a dynamic grid model would increase the system order, and alter the system response. Nevertheless, the proposed classification and associated frequency services remains conceptually valid, and future research should extend this framework to include dynamic grid models for a more comprehensive system-level analysis.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ander Ordone: Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Javier Rodriguez-Gongora:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Investigation. **Alain Sanchez-Ruiz:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Markel Zubiaga:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Francisco Javier Asensio:** Supervision. **Jose Antonio Cortajarena:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Grid connected mode transfer functions

$\Delta P / \Delta P^*$, $\Delta P / \Delta \omega_r$ and $\Delta \omega_r / \Delta \Phi$ are summarized in Table A.10. The term β refers to the characteristic equation, which is the numerator of $s + G_c H_c \omega_b K_T$.

Appendix B. Primary frequency regulation impact on τ_z

If the natural frequency and the phase margin of the system are fixed, a PSL with primary frequency regulation requires a smaller τ_z than a PSL without it. This is proofed for the gain + pole + zero structure, which includes primary frequency regulation (subscript 1), and the gain + pole at origin + zero structure, without it (subscript 2).

Starting from the characteristic equation from Table A.10, the natural frequency terms can be equated, leading to (B.1). Additionally, since the damping coefficients (or equivalently, the phase margins) are the same, the terms involving s can also be equated, resulting in (B.2).

$$K_2 = \frac{K_1}{\tau_{p1}} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$\tau_{z2} K_2 K_T \omega_b = \frac{\tau_{z1} K_1 K_T \omega_b}{\tau_{p1}} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

By manipulating these two equations, the relationship between τ_{z1} and τ_{z2} is derived, demonstrating that $\tau_{z2} > \tau_{z1}$:

$$\tau_{z2} = \tau_{z1} + \frac{1}{K_1 K_T \omega_b} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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